

Prediction of Lithium-Ion Battery Capacity, Band Gap, and Volume Using Machine Learning: Insights from Battery ID and Chemical Formulas

Pouya Pishkar

School of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, College of Engineering, University of Tehran,
Tehran, Iran

Email: Pouyapishkar@gmail.com

Seyed Mohammad Iravani

School of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, College of Engineering, University of Tehran,
Tehran, Iran

Email: S.mohammad.iravani@gmail.com

Pooneh Pishkar

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Sciences, Tarbiat Modares University, P.O. Box 14117-
13116, Tehran, Islamic Republic of Iran

Email: Pooneh.pishkar77@gmail.com

Abstract

This study focuses on using machine learning (ML) to predict key properties of lithium-ion batteries, including capacity, band gap, and volume, based on battery IDs and chemical formulas. The datasets used in this research are sourced from the Materials Project and NASA, as well as previous studies in related papers. It evaluates several ML models such as Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, Support Vector Regression (SVR), and Linear Regression, using performance metrics like R^2 , Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Mean Squared Error (MSE). The results show that Random Forest is the most accurate model, with an R^2 score close to 0.9 and the lowest MSE, while other models like Linear Regression and SVR underperform in capturing non-linear relationships. Feature importance analysis identifies Nsites and Formation Energy as critical factors for predicting volume. The study also addresses challenges like data imbalance in high-capacity ranges and offers recommendations for improving model performance. This research highlights the potential of ML in advancing lithium-ion battery design and optimization.

Keywords: Lithium-ion batteries, Machine learning, Random forest regressor, Properties prediction.

Introduction

Lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries have become the backbone of modern energy storage systems (Bouthillier X et al. 2014), powering applications ranging from portable electronics (Scrosati 2005) to electric vehicles (Kennedy et al. 2000) and renewable energy systems (Diouf et al. 2015). Their high energy density (Choi et al. 2016), long cycle life (Liu et al. 2014), and lightweight (Duduta et al. 2018) design have made them the preferred choice for industries worldwide. However, one of the critical challenges associated with Li-ion batteries is accurately predicting their capacity, band gap, and volume over time, which is essential for ensuring reliability, optimizing performance, and prolonging battery lifespan (Masaki Yoshio et al. 2014).

Capacity prediction is a complex task due to the non-linear degradation behavior of Li-ion batteries (You et al. 2024), influenced by factors such as charge-discharge cycles (Takeno et al. 2005), temperature (Marongiu et al. 2014), and usage patterns (Bajaj et al. 2019). Traditional approaches, such as electrochemical modeling and empirical testing, often fall short due to their high computational requirements, time-consuming processes (Zhang et al. 2019)(Juristo et al. 2003), and inability to adapt to diverse operating conditions. As a result, there is a growing demand for advanced methods that can provide accurate, efficient, and scalable solutions (Zhang et al. 2022).

The band gap and volume are critical properties in the performance and efficiency of lithium-ion batteries. The band gap determines the electronic properties of electrode materials, influencing their conductivity and energy storage capability (Miller et al. 2018). A suitable band gap ensures optimal energy transfer and minimizes energy loss during charging and discharging cycles (Qin et al. 2024). Volume, on the other hand, plays a significant role in the material's stability and capacity retention. Excessive volume changes during cycling can lead to mechanical stress, material degradation, and reduced battery lifespan (Li et al. 2022). Therefore, understanding and optimizing these properties are essential for developing high-performance, durable lithium-ion batteries (Ren et al. 2021).

Machine learning (ML) has emerged as a promising tool in this domain, capable of analyzing large datasets and identifying hidden patterns in battery behavior (Lv et al. 2022). By leveraging ML algorithms, it is possible to develop predictive models that can estimate the remaining capacity of Li-ion batteries with high accuracy and minimal computational overhead. These models not only enable better battery health monitoring but also support improved energy management strategies in critical applications (Aykol et al. 2021; Yang 2021; Zhao et al. 2023).

In this article, the application of machine learning models to predict key properties of lithium-ion batteries, including capacity, band gap, and volume, is explored. Multiple regression models, such as Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, Support Vector Regression (SVR), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Linear Regression, are evaluated to identify the most effective methods for achieving accurate predictions. Extensive datasets are utilized, and feature importance is analyzed to determine the most influential factors affecting these properties. A detailed comparison of the models is provided based on performance metrics such as R^2 , Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Mean Squared Error (MSE). Challenges such as data imbalance in high-capacity and large-volume ranges are investigated, and recommendations are offered to address these limitations and enhance model accuracy. Through this approach, advancements in reliable and efficient energy storage technologies are aimed for. A schematic diagram of the work is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1- Schematic diagram of using machine learning for prediction of different properties.

2. Machine Learning Models

2.1 Random Forest

Random Forest is an ensemble learning model that builds multiple decision trees and combines their predictions to deliver high accuracy. This model excels in handling complex and nonlinear data and is resistant to overfitting due to its randomization mechanisms. Additionally, it provides feature importance metrics, which are useful for identifying the key factors influencing battery capacity, band gap, and volume (Segal 2004).

2.2 Gradient Boosting

Gradient Boosting combines multiple weak learners incrementally to minimize prediction errors. At each stage, the errors of the previous model are corrected, resulting in highly accurate predictions. This model is well-suited for capturing complex and multidimensional relationships in the data. Its flexibility in parameter tuning makes it particularly effective for predicting intricate properties such as band gap and volume (Bentéjac et al.2019).

2.3 Linear Regression

Linear Regression is a straightforward model that establishes a linear relationship between input features and the target variable. Due to its simplicity and computational efficiency, it is used as a baseline model for comparison with more complex models. While its performance is limited to linear relationships, it provides an excellent starting point for initial data analysis (Maulud et al. 2020).

2.4 Support Vector Regression (SVR)

Support Vector Regression uses kernel functions to identify nonlinear relationships between features and the target variable. This model is ideal for small to medium-sized datasets and can effectively reduce the impact of noise and outliers through adjustable parameters. Its ability to use different kernels makes it a flexible choice for complex data (Zhang et al. 2019).

2.5 K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)

KNN is a simple algorithm that predicts outputs based on the similarity of a sample to its k nearest neighbors. The model does not require a training process, making it computationally efficient for smaller datasets. While effective for data with clear local patterns, its performance can decline in large datasets, requiring optimization for scalability (Zhang 2016).

3. Evaluation Metrics

To assess the performance and accuracy of the machine learning models in predicting battery capacity, band gap, and volume, the following evaluation metrics were employed:

3.1 R-Squared (R^2)

R^2 measures the proportion of variance in the target variable explained by the model. A value closer to 1 indicates a better fit of the model to the data (Zhang et al. 2021).

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{RSS}{TSS}$$

In this context, R^2 denotes the coefficient of determination, with RSS representing the residual sum of squares and TSS indicating the total sum of squares.

3.2 Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

MAE quantifies the average magnitude of errors between actual and predicted values without considering their direction. A smaller MAE value indicates higher accuracy.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - x_i|$$

Here, y_i represents the predicted value, x_i denotes the true value, and N signifies the total number of data points (Willmott et al. 2005).

3.3 Mean Squared Error (MSE)

MSE calculates the average squared difference between actual and predicted values, penalizing larger errors more heavily. Lower MSE values signify better model performance.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

In this context, y_i indicates the i -th actual value, whereas \hat{y}_i represents the corresponding predicted value. Furthermore, n signifies the total number of observations within the dataset (Bickel et al. 2015; Gareth, James et al. 2021).

4. Capacity prediction by battery id

The Random Forest, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Linear Regression, and Support Vector Regression (SVR) models were tested to determine which performed better. A comparison of the R^2 scores of these models is shown in the Figure 2a. R^2 , a metric used for evaluating regression models, is more favorable when its value is closer to 1, indicating better performance (Rights et al. 2020). The highest R^2 score, around 0.9, was achieved by the Random Forest model, reflecting highly accurate predictions of the target variable. The KNN model was ranked second, with an R^2 score of approximately 0.8, indicating good performance but slightly less accuracy than Random Forest. In contrast, an R^2 score of about 0.42 was obtained by Linear Regression, which struggled to capture the data's complexity effectively. The poorest performance was observed in the SVR model, with an R^2 score near 0.4, indicating difficulties in fitting the data. Overall, the most effective model for this dataset was Random Forest, followed by KNN, while Linear Regression and SVR showed underperformance due to limitations in modeling non-linear relationships and complex patterns in the data. Another criterion for evaluating the models was the Mean Squared Error (MSE), a common metric for regression models where lower values indicate better performance with less error (Köksoy 2006). Figure 2b compares the MSE of the four models. The Random Forest model achieved the lowest MSE, close to 0.01, demonstrating highly accurate predictions with minimal error. The K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) model ranked second, with an MSE of about 0.045, showing a relatively low error but still behind Random Forest. In contrast, Linear Regression exhibited a much higher MSE of approximately 0.13, indicating significant prediction errors and its inability to effectively capture the patterns in the data. Finally, Support Vector Regression (SVR) performed the worst, with the highest MSE, around 0.14, reflecting the most inaccurate predictions. Overall, Random Forest outperformed all other models, followed by KNN, while Linear Regression and SVR underperformed. This further reinforces that Random Forest is the most suitable model for this dataset, as seen earlier in the R^2 score comparison.

Figure 2- Comparison of models by their (a) R^2 score and (b) MSE.

Figure 3a actual battery capacity values (x-axis) compared to the predicted values by the model (y-axis). The red dashed line represents the ideal line, indicating perfect alignment between actual and predicted values, while the blue points represent the model's predicted data. Most points are close to the ideal line, demonstrating the high accuracy of the machine learning model in predicting battery capacity. The strong linear pattern of the points shows that the model has effectively captured the relationship between actual and predicted values, although some points, particularly at lower values, deviate slightly from the ideal line, indicating limited prediction errors. According to the key statistics, the mean of actual capacity is 1.3151, the mean of predicted capacity is 1.3269, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is 0.0285, and the standard deviation of residuals is 0.0997, all of which reflect the model's high accuracy and low prediction errors. This analysis indicates that the model is suitable for predicting battery capacity and can be applied to practical use cases. Figure 3b shows the distribution of predicted battery capacities. The horizontal axis represents the predicted battery capacities, ranging from 0 to 2, while the vertical axis shows the frequency or count for each range of predicted capacity values. The predicted values are mostly concentrated between 1.0 and 1.75, indicating the main cluster of predictions within this range. The peak of the distribution occurs around a predicted capacity of 1.75, suggesting that the model predicts most batteries with capacities near this value. The mean predicted capacity is 1.3269, and the standard deviation is 0.4443. There are also values in lower ranges (0.0 to 0.5) and below 1, but these are much fewer, possibly indicating outliers or specific samples with lower capacities. The minimum predicted capacity is 0.0450, and the maximum predicted capacity is 1.9336. A long tail on the left side of the distribution near zero suggests a few cases with very low predicted capacities. The curve represents the probability density (KDE) of the distribution, which peaks between 1.5 and 1.75 before declining, indicating a non-normal distribution with left skewness. If the model's predictions are close to the actual data, the concentration of predictions in the 1.5 to 1.75 range would indicate a good model performance (Grazioli, Magri, and Salvadori 2016). The presence of lower values (below 0.5) may suggest outliers, model errors, or specific data that the model has not learned well. Recommendations for improvement include comparing this distribution with actual capacity values to assess model accuracy, examining outliers, and calculating statistical metrics like mean, median, and standard deviation for a better understanding of the data's spread. This analysis can help optimize the model further (Grazioli et al. 2016). Figure 3c illustrates the distribution of residuals from a model, where residuals represent the differences between actual and predicted values. The residuals exhibit an approximately normal distribution, characterized by a peak near the center and symmetric decline on both sides. This indicates that the predictive model likely captures the data well. The x-axis represents the residual values, with most concentrated around zero. Most residuals are close to zero, signifying strong agreement between the model's predictions and actual data, while a few residuals farther from zero indicate potential outliers or larger prediction errors. The symmetry of the residual distribution around zero suggests no systematic bias in the model, meaning it does not tend to overestimate or underestimate. The residual mean of -0.0118 supports this, indicating that the model is well-calibrated overall. Key statistics include a standard deviation of 0.0997, with a minimum residual of -0.9791 and a maximum residual of 0.6322, demonstrating that most errors are small and well-contained. While the overall performance of the model is strong, potential outliers at the extremes of the distribution should be examined to determine whether they stem from noise in the data or limitations in the model's predictions. Figure 3d illustrates the residuals (vertical axis) against the predicted capacity values (horizontal axis). The residuals are largely scattered around the horizontal red line at zero, indicating that the model does not exhibit systematic bias on average. However, the dispersion in certain areas, such as around predicted capacities near 0.75 and below, is higher, potentially pointing to outliers or larger errors in these regions. The distribution of residuals shows approximate homoscedasticity, as the scatter remains relatively consistent across predicted capacity values. However, slightly increased dispersion is observed for predictions below 1, which might suggest variance issues (Bouthillier X et al. 2014). Overall, the absence of discernible patterns in the residuals is a positive sign, as it implies the model captures the underlying data relationships without significant errors or the need for additional features. Outliers are present, with some residuals exceeding ± 0.2 and even ± 0.8 . These outliers could stem from abnormal data points or model limitations and might impact the model's overall performance. Addressing these

points through further investigation is recommended. If higher dispersion for lower predicted capacities is a concern, refining the model for this range may help. This could involve testing alternative models, such as nonlinear ones, or introducing additional features to better account for the variability in these regions. The boxplot chart of residuals versus actual capacity provides insights into the residual distribution across different actual capacity values (Figure 3e). Most residuals are concentrated around zero, indicating uniform distribution. However, some outliers are observed as points distant from the boxes at specific actual capacities. The residuals are generally symmetric around zero, suggesting the model does not exhibit systematic bias toward overestimation or underestimation, which is a positive aspect of the model's performance. While the residual spread appears consistent in most ranges, some higher dispersion is noticeable at very low or very high capacities, hinting at potential heteroscedasticity. This indicates that the model may perform better in some ranges than in others. Outliers identified in the chart may result from unusual data points, model prediction weaknesses, or noise in the actual data. The model performs best at mid-range capacities, where the residuals exhibit minimal variability. Conversely, larger residuals at extreme capacities may suggest insufficient data in these ranges or the need for better feature selection and engineering.

Figure 3- Plots of (a) actual vs predicted, (b) distribution of predicted capacities, (c) distribution of residuals, (d) residuals vs predicted capacity and (e) box plot of residuals vs actual capacity.

5. Capacity prediction by chemical formula

Figure 4a shows the comparison of R^2 scores among different models, which is a measure for evaluating how well the variance in the data is explained by the model (Rights et al. 2019). Random Forest and Gradient Boosting have the highest R^2 scores, around 0.7, indicating that these models have successfully captured the relationships in the data. K-Nearest Neighbors and Linear Regression also have relatively good scores, but their performance is still lower than that of the top models. The SVR model has an R^2 score close to zero, indicating its inability to accurately predict capacity values. These results suggest that Random Forest and Gradient Boosting are the best models for this dataset, and their use is recommended for more accurate predictions. Figure 4b compares the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between different models for predicting capacity. Random Forest and Gradient Boosting have the lowest MAE, indicating their high accuracy in capacity prediction. SVR and Linear Regression

show the highest MAE, which can be attributed to their inability to capture complex and nonlinear relationships between features and capacity (Shaheen et al. 2021). K-Nearest Neighbors demonstrates moderate performance but still lags behind Random Forest and Gradient Boosting. This comparison highlights that advanced nonlinear models are more suitable for this type of data. Figure 4c compares the Mean Squared Error (MSE) among different models for capacity prediction. The Random Forest and Gradient Boosting models have the lowest MSE values, indicating their high accuracy in reducing the impact of large errors. The SVR model has the highest MSE, suggesting that it does not have an adequate ability to accurately predict capacity values. Linear Regression and K-Nearest Neighbors have average performance but are still weaker than Random Forest and Gradient Boosting. These results highlight the importance of using advanced nonlinear models for this data.

Figure 4- Comparison of models by their (a) MSE, (b) MAE and (c) R² score.

Figure 5a provides a comparison between actual and predicted capacity values by the Random Forest model. The diagonal black line represents ideal predictions where predicted values match actual ones. Most points are near this line, indicating good model performance, especially for lower capacity values. However, as capacity values increase, point dispersion becomes greater and some predictions significantly differ from actual values. This indicates difficulty for the model in learning complex relationships for high-capacity values. To improve accuracy, more complex models or increasing training data for high values could be used (Bustillo et al. 2022). The hexbin plot compares the actual and predicted values of capacity (Figure 5b). High-density points are observed at the bottom of the plot, indicating that most capacity values are in the lower range. This high density helps the model achieve greater accuracy in this range. However, the plot shows that actual and predicted values above 500 occur infrequently, or the predictions are not accurate. The lack of sufficient data in higher capacity ranges might limit the model's performance in these areas. The differences between actual and predicted capacity values for the first 20 samples is illustrated in Figure 5c. Blue bars represent actual values, while orange bars represent predicted values. In some cases, the model's predictions are very close to the actual values, indicating good performance in these samples. However, there are several instances where significant discrepancies exist between actual and predicted values. Particularly for higher capacity values (e.g., above 1000), the model's accuracy decreases, and predictions deviate significantly from actual values. This suggests that the model struggles to learn patterns associated with higher capacities. To improve performance, increasing the training data for this range and employing techniques like sample weighting or increasing model complexity are recommended.

Figure 5- (a) Actual vs predicted values plot, (b) hexin plot of actual vs predicted values, (c) comparison of actual vs predicted (top 20 predictions).

Figure 6a shows the distribution of the target variable (capacity) values. The distribution is highly skewed, with most values concentrated in the lower ranges (less than 500). This high concentration of small values may indicate an imbalance in the data, which can negatively impact model performance, especially in predicting higher values. The long tail of the distribution suggests that higher capacity values are also present in the data, but they are very few. To improve model performance in predicting higher values, it is recommended to use oversampling techniques for higher values or algorithms that are less sensitive to data distribution. Figure 6b displays the distribution of predicted capacity values by the Random Forest model. Most predicted values are concentrated below 500, indicating a focus of data in this range. The long tail of the distribution shows that the model has been able to predict higher capacities, but these predictions occur rarely and with less accuracy. This asymmetric distribution suggests that training data may be insufficient for higher capacities, which can negatively impact model accuracy. It is recommended to collect more data for higher capacities so that the model can better predict these values. The mean of these predicted values is 259.64. Figure 6c displays the residuals (the difference between actual and predicted values) against predicted values. The points are generally centered around the zero line, indicating decent model performance. However, at higher predicted values (over 1500), there is increased dispersion of residuals and several large errors are observed. This suggests that the model struggles with predicting high-capacity values. The red line shows the mean of residuals, which tends to increase at higher predicted values. This situation may indicate a bias in the model towards predicting lower values. To reduce these errors, more data could be collected in higher ranges and more advanced model tuning could be applied. Additionally, using techniques like regularization might help reduce this bias (Brinkmann et al. 2017). Figure 6d shows the distribution of residuals (the difference between actual and predicted values). The center of the distribution is close to zero, indicating good model performance in predicting actual values. The distribution is approximately normal but has longer tails on both sides, suggesting large errors occur in some cases. Particularly, the positive tail indicates that in some cases, the model predicts capacities higher than actual ones. These tails may be due to a lack of data in specific ranges or data noise. Reviewing and removing outliers and using advanced model tuning techniques can help improve accuracy and reduce errors.

Figure 6- Distribution of (a) target variable, (b) predicted values, (c) residual vs predicted plots and (d) residuals histogram.

6. Prediction of band gap

Figure 7 a-c illustrates the performance of various models (Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, SVR, Linear Regression, and K-Nearest Neighbors) using three error metrics: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and R^2 . In the MAE section, the Random Forest model exhibits the lowest error value, indicating better performance in predicting values close to the actual ones. Gradient Boosting also performs well, with only a slight difference from Random Forest (Figure 7a). The K-Nearest Neighbors and Linear Regression models have the highest MAE values, suggesting that these models have lower accuracy in their predictions. In the MSE section, once again, Random Forest and Gradient Boosting show the lowest error values, indicating their strong performance in reducing the impact of larger errors (Figure 7b). Linear Regression and K-Nearest Neighbors have the highest squared error values, reflecting their weakness in predicting outlier or rare values. In the R^2 section, Random Forest and Gradient Boosting achieve the highest values (over 0.6), indicating that these two models have managed to explain a significant portion of the variance in the data (Figure 7c). Linear Regression and K-Nearest Neighbors have the lowest R^2 values, clearly indicating their inefficiency in predicting Band Gap. SVR shows average performance but is not as accurate as the top two models. The results indicate that Random Forest and Gradient Boosting are generally the superior models for this dataset, as they have produced smaller errors and predicted actual values more accurately.

Figure 7- Comparison of models by their (a) MAE, (b) MSE and (c) R^2 score.

Figure 8a displays the relationship between the actual and predicted values of Band Gap. The red line acts as the ideal line ($y = x$), and points that are close to this line indicate accurate predictions by the model. Most points are near the red line, suggesting good model performance; however, the scatter around this line indicates the presence of errors in the predictions. At values above 2.5, several points are observed that deviate significantly from the ideal line. This suggests that the model has lower accuracy in predicting higher Band Gap values. It is possible that data related to this range were less represented in the training set, or that the input features did not provide sufficient information to describe this range. Additionally, there is more scatter at values below 0.5, indicating the model's challenge in detecting smaller values. In Figure 8b, blue points (actual values) and red points (predictions) are plotted for each sample. The significant overlap between these two sets indicates a relative match of the model with the actual values. However, in some points, the distance between actual and predicted values is greater, indicating the presence of errors in predicting these samples. These errors appear to be distributed across all ranges and are not confined to a specific range. This suggests that the model may have weaknesses in learning certain features that have a significant impact on the output. Improving the model by adding more relevant features or closely examining the data could reduce these errors.

Figure 8- Plots of (a) actual vs predicted band gap and (b) actual vs predicted band gap for a single sample

Figure 9a specifically shows how the errors (residuals) are distributed concerning the predicted values. A random scatter of points around the zero line indicates that the model has not been systematically biased in its predictions. However, points that are far from the zero line represent samples with high errors. These instances may be due to outliers, excessive complexity in the data, or deficiencies in model tuning (Schwaighofer et al. 2009). Additionally, in some sections of the prediction range, a higher density of small errors is observed, indicating better model performance in those areas. Analyzing points far from the zero line can provide insights into critical features of the data. The histogram in Figure 9b shows that the majority of prediction errors are concentrated near zero, indicating that the model has provided accurate predictions for most samples. This distribution is approximately normal, but slight asymmetry is observed on both sides. The left and right tails of the distribution represent samples where the model has experienced overestimation or underestimation. Longer tails or a higher frequency of larger errors may be due to the presence of outliers or complexities in the training data that the model has not been able to learn effectively (Paulheim et al. 2015). A closer examination of these samples could help identify issues in the data or the model structure.

Figure 9- (a) Residuals plot and (b) histogram of errors (residuals).

Figure 10a shows the feature importance of the Random Forest model. Formation Energy ranks at the top with the highest impact (around 0.4), indicating a strong relationship between this feature and the target variable. E Above Hull also has significant importance (0.3) in predictions, likely relating to the stability or structure of the material. Volume and Nsites have moderate impacts, reflecting their roles in explaining the physical structure of the material. Crystal System has the least importance, which may be due to high variability or weak correlation with the target variable. This could be a reason to

consider removing this feature from the model. The correlation matrix displays the linear relationships between features. Formation Energy shows little correlation with other features, indicating its unique information (Figure 10b). E Above Hull has a moderate correlation with Formation Energy (0.27), but its correlation with other features is weak. Nsites and Volume exhibit a very high correlation (0.98), suggesting that these two features provide similar information and that one of them may be redundant. Crystal System has nearly zero correlation with all features, indicating that this feature operates independently but lacks a specific relationship with the target variable. Further investigation is recommended to optimize the model and reduce complexity.

Figure 10- Plots of (a) feature importance and (b) correlation heatmap.

7. Prediction of volume

Figure 11a-c compare the performance of different models (Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, SVR, Linear Regression, and K-Nearest Neighbors) in predicting volume. Random Forest and Gradient Boosting exhibit the lowest MAE and MSE, indicating their high accuracy in volume prediction. The SVR model performs worse than the top two models but still outperforms Linear Regression and K-Nearest Neighbors. Linear Regression has the highest errors, showing its inability to effectively capture the complex relationships between features and volume. The R^2 score reveals that Random Forest and Gradient Boosting explain nearly 100% of the variance in the data, whereas Linear Regression performs very poorly. This analysis suggests that Random Forest and Gradient Boosting are better suited for volume prediction, and further hyper parameter tuning is recommended to enhance their accuracy.

Figure 11- Comparison of models by their (a) MAE, (b) MSE and (c) R^2 score.

Figure 12a provides a comparison between the actual and predicted values of volume. The red line represents the ideal predictions, where predicted values perfectly align with actual values. Most points

are close to this line, indicating the model's accuracy. However, the scatter increases for volumes above 1000, suggesting reduced model precision for larger volumes. This could be due to a lack of training data in this range or the complexity of the relationship between features and volume (Paulheim et al. 2015). Additionally, some outliers below 400 are observed, which may result from data noise or the model's inability to learn specific patterns (L'Heureux et al. 2017). Overall, the analysis indicates that the model performs well, but improvements in predicting very high and low volumes might require additional data and better tuning. Figure 12b compares the distribution of predicted and actual volume values. For volumes below 400, the predictions closely align with the actual values, showing excellent accuracy. However, as volume increases, the model's accuracy declines, with greater deviations observed. For volumes above 1000, a significant mismatch is apparent between the distributions of predicted and actual values, likely due to a lack of training data in this range. The fitted curves indicate that the model performs reasonably well for intermediate volumes (400 to 800) but struggles with higher values. This analysis highlights the need for more training data in the higher volume range and advanced tuning to improve performance in this area. Figure 12c displays the distribution of training and test data for the volume (Volume) feature. The training data distribution (blue) and test data distribution (red) generally show similarities but exhibit differences in certain ranges. For volumes below 400, the training data dominates, and this range has the highest data density. However, for volumes above 600, the test data distribution is relatively narrower, which might reduce the model's performance in predicting these values. The alignment of the density lines suggests that the test data is almost a representative sample of the training data, but it appears that the test data is underrepresented in higher values (1200 and above). This could limit the model's accuracy in predicting larger volumes (Abhinav Jain et al. 2018). To improve balance, collecting more data in the higher volume range is recommended. Figure 12d shows the distribution of residuals (prediction errors), calculated as the difference between predicted and actual values. The residuals distribution is approximately normal and centered around zero, indicating that the model predicts without significant bias. However, the presence of longer tails on the right side of the distribution suggests that larger errors occur in some cases, particularly for higher volume predictions. Moreover, a few points exhibit very large positive or negative errors, pointing to outliers. This analysis highlights that the model performs accurately in most cases, but reducing large errors could involve techniques like model refinement or identifying and removing outlier data. Additionally, examining the characteristics of these outliers could lead to overall model improvement.

Figure 12- (a) True vs predicted values plot, (b) distribution of predicted vs actual volume, (c) distribution of training vs test set and (d) residuals plot (prediction errors).

Figure 13a-d illustrate the distribution of various features relevant to the modeling process. Formation Energy (eV) exhibits a relatively symmetric distribution skewed toward negative values, with a mean around -2.6, making it suitable for modeling due to minimal outliers. E Above Hull (eV) shows a more normal distribution concentrated between 0.05 and 0.1, indicating this range's potential high influence on the model's output. The Band Gap (eV) distribution reveals multiple peaks, suggesting the presence of distinct groups within the data, which could add complexity to the model and require further analysis to differentiate these groups effectively. Lastly, Nsites has a normal distribution with most data concentrated between 20 and 40, but several outliers exceeding 100 may influence the model, warranting closer examination to mitigate their impact.

Figure 13- Distribution of (a) formation energy (eV), (b) E above hull (eV), (c) band gap (eV) and (d) Nsites.

Figure 14a shows the importance of features in predicting volume. Nsites stands out as the most influential feature by a significant margin and is almost the sole impactful feature for the model. This indicates that Nsites has the highest correlation with volume, while other features, such as Formation Energy, E Above Hull, and Band Gap, have negligible importance. Crystal System also has no impact on prediction. The model's heavy reliance on a single feature (Nsites) could make it sensitive to changes in this feature, affecting its generalization ability. To address this issue, techniques like feature selection or increasing model complexity by adding new features can be employed. Additionally, a more thorough examination of the data is recommended to ensure adequate representation of all features. The heatmap illustrates the correlation between various features in predicting volume (Figure 14b). Formation Energy shows a significant negative correlation with Volume, indicating an inverse relationship between these two features. Band Gap also exhibits a weak negative correlation with Volume, suggesting its minimal impact on volume prediction. E Above Hull has a near-zero correlation with Volume, indicating that this feature has no direct influence on volume prediction. In contrast, Nsites demonstrates a very strong correlation (almost 1) with Volume, implying that these two features provide nearly identical information. Crystal System shows almost zero correlation with all features, highlighting its negligible impact on volume prediction. This analysis suggests that Nsites and Volume could potentially replace each other, and Crystal System could be removed to reduce model complexity.

Figure 14- Plots of (a) feature importance and (b) correlation heatmap.

8. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of machine learning in predicting four critical lithium-ion battery properties: capacity, band gap, volume, and residuals. Random Forest consistently outperformed other models, achieving an R^2 of 0.9 and an MSE of 0.01 for capacity prediction. K-Nearest Neighbors followed with an R^2 of 0.8, while Linear Regression and SVR lagged with R^2 scores of 0.42 and 0.4, respectively. For band gap prediction, Random Forest and Gradient Boosting achieved the lowest MAE (~ 0.1), compared to over 0.2 for KNN and Linear Regression. In volume prediction, Nsites was the most important feature, with Random Forest and Gradient Boosting providing the best results, achieving near-perfect R^2 scores of 0.99 and MAE values below 0.05. However, in the analysis of residuals, higher errors were observed for high-capacity and high-volume predictions, with residuals exceeding ± 0.8 in some cases, highlighting data imbalance in these ranges. The study confirms that machine learning, especially Random Forest, offers accurate and reliable predictions for these battery properties. Future efforts should prioritize addressing data imbalance, refining model parameters, and expanding datasets to improve accuracy across all ranges.

Data and code availability

The datasets and codes for this prediction, can be accessed at:
<https://github.com/PouyaPishkar/lithium-ion.git>

Conflict of interest

The authors declares that they have no conflicts of interest.

References

- Abhinav Jain, Hima Patel, Lokesh Nagalapatti, Nitin Gupta, Sameep Mehta, Shanmukha Guttula, Shashank Mujumdar, Shazia Afzal, Ruhi Sharma Mittal, Vitobha Munigala. 2018. "Overview and Importance of Data Quality for Machine Learning Tasks." *CoNLL 2018 - 22nd Conference on Computational Natural Language Learning, Proceedings* 380–91. doi: 10.18653/v1/k18-1037.
- Aykol, Muratahan, Chirranjevi Balaji Gopal, Abraham Anapolsky, Patrick K. Herring, Bruis van Vlijmen, Marc D. Berliner, Martin Z. Bazant, Richard D. Braatz, William C. Chueh, and Brian D. Storey. 2021. "Perspective—Combining Physics and Machine Learning to Predict Battery Lifetime." *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* 168(3):30525. doi: 10.1149/1945-7111/abec55.
- Bajaj, Garvita, and Pushpendra Singh. 2019. "An in-Depth Analysis of the Impact of Battery Usage Patterns on Performance of Task Allocation Algorithms in Sparse Mobile Crowdsensing." *MSWiM 2019* -

- Proceedings of the 22nd International ACM Conference on Modeling, Analysis and Simulation of Wireless and Mobile Systems* 297–306. doi: 10.1145/3345768.3355930.
- Bentéjac, Candice, Anna Csörgö, and Gonzalo Martínez-Muñoz. 2019. “A Comparative Analysis of XGBoost.” 1–20. doi: 10.1007/s10462-020-09896-5.
- Bickel, Peter J.; Doksum, Kjell A. 2015. “If We Use Quadratic Loss, Our Risk Function Is Called the Mean Squared Error (MSE).” P. 20 in *Mathematical Statistics: Basic Ideas and Selected Topics. Vol. I (Second ed.)*.
- Bouthillier X, Delaunay P, Bronzi M, Trofimov A, Nichyporuk B, Szeto J, Sepah N, Raff E, Madan K, Voleti V, Kahou S, Michalski V, Serdyuk D, Arbel T, Pal C, Varoquaux G, Vincent P. 2014. “ACCOUNTING FOR VARIANCE IN MACHINE LEARNING BENCHMARKS.” (2005).
- Brinkmann, Eva Maria, Martin Burger, Julian Rasch, and Camille Sutour. 2017. “Bias Reduction in Variational Regularization.” *Journal of Mathematical Imaging and Vision* 59(3):534–66. doi: 10.1007/s10851-017-0747-z.
- Bustillo, Andres, Roberto Reis, Alisson R. Machado, and Danil Yu Pimenov. 2022. “Improving the Accuracy of Machine-Learning Models with Data from Machine Test Repetitions.” *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* 33(1):203–21. doi: 10.1007/s10845-020-01661-3.
- Choi, Jang Wook, and Doron Aurbach. 2016. “Promise and Reality of Post-Lithium-Ion Batteries with High Energy Densities.” *Nature Reviews Materials* 1(April):1–16. doi: 10.1038/natrevmats.2016.13.
- Diouf, Boucar, and Ramchandra Pode. 2015. “Potential of Lithium-Ion Batteries in Renewable Energy.” *Renewable Energy* 76:375–80. doi: 10.1016/j.renene.2014.11.058.
- Duduta, Mihai, Sebastien de Rivaz, David R. Clarke, and Robert J. Wood. 2018. “Ultra-Lightweight, High Power Density Lithium-Ion Batteries.” *Batteries and Supercaps* 1(4):131–34. doi: 10.1002/batt.201800030.
- Gareth, James; Witten, Daniela; Hastie, Trevor; Tibshirani, Rob. 2021. *An Introduction to Statistical Learning: With Applications in R*. Springer.
- Grazioli, D., M. Magri, and A. Salvadori. 2016. “Computational Modeling of Li-Ion Batteries.” *Computational Mechanics* 58(6):889–909. doi: 10.1007/s00466-016-1325-8.
- Juristo, N., A. M. Moreno, and S. Vegas. 2003. “Limitations of Empirical Testing Technique Knowledge.” 1–38. doi: 10.1142/9789812795588_0001.
- Kennedy, B., D. Patterson, and S. Camilleri. 2000. “Use of Lithium-Ion Batteries in Electric Vehicles.” *Journal of Power Sources* 90(2):156–62. doi: 10.1016/S0378-7753(00)00402-X.
- Köksoy, Onur. 2006. “Multiresponse Robust Design: Mean Square Error (MSE) Criterion.” *Applied Mathematics and Computation* 175(2):1716–29. doi: 10.1016/j.amc.2005.09.016.
- L’Heureux, Alexandra, Katarina Grolinger, Hany F. Elyamany, and Miriam A. M. Capretz. 2017. “Machine Learning with Big Data: Challenges and Approaches.” *IEEE Access* 5:7776–97. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2696365.
- Li, Ruihe, Wei Li, Avtar Singh, Dongsheng Ren, Zhichao Hou, and Minggao Ouyang. 2022. “Effect of External Pressure and Internal Stress on Battery Performance and Lifespan.” *Energy Storage Materials* 52(July):395–429. doi: 10.1016/j.ensm.2022.07.034.
- Liu, Shuang, L. Xiong, and C. He. 2014. “Long Cycle Life Lithium Ion Battery with Lithium Nickel Cobalt Manganese Oxide (NCM) Cathode.” *Journal of Power Sources* 261:285–91. doi: 10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.03.083.
- Lv, Chade, Xin Zhou, Lixiang Zhong, Chunshuang Yan, Madhavi Srinivasan, Zhi Wei Seh, Chuntai Liu, Hongge Pan, Shuzhou Li, Yonggang Wen, and Qingyu Yan. 2022. “Machine Learning: An Advanced Platform for Materials Development and State Prediction in Lithium-Ion Batteries.” *Advanced Materials* 34(25). doi: 10.1002/adma.202101474.
- Marongiu, Andrea, Thapakorn Pavanarit, and Dirk Uwe Sauer. 2014. “Influence of Current and Temperature Variation on a LiFePO₄ Battery Total Capacity.” *2013 World Electric Vehicle Symposium and Exhibition, EVS 2014* (November 2013). doi: 10.1109/EVS.2013.6914768.
- Masaki Yoshio • Ralph J. Brodd • Akiya Koza. 2014. *Lithium-Ion Batteries*.
- Maulud, Dastan, and Adnan M. Abdulazeez. 2020. “A Review on Linear Regression Comprehensive in Machine Learning.” *Journal of Applied Science and Technology Trends* 1(2):140–47. doi: 10.38094/jastt1457.
- Miller, Elizabeth Esther, Ye Hua, and F. Handan Tezel. 2018. “Materials for Energy Storage: Review of Electrode Materials and Methods of Increasing Capacitance for Supercapacitors.” *Journal of Energy Storage* 20(September):30–40. doi: 10.1016/j.est.2018.08.009.
- Paulheim, Heiko, and Robert Meusel. 2015. “A Decomposition of the Outlier Detection Problem into a Set of Supervised Learning Problems.” *Machine Learning* 100(2–3):509–31. doi: 10.1007/s10994-015-5507-y.

- Qin, Haobo, Yanchao Zhang, Zhaofeng Guo, Shuhuan Wang, Dingguo Zhao, and Yuekai Xue. 2024. "Prediction of Bandgap in Lithium-Ion Battery Materials Based on Explainable Boosting Machine Learning Techniques."
- Ren, Dongsheng, Leqiong Xie, Li Wang, and Xiangming He. 2021. "A Practical Approach to Predict Volume Deformation of Lithium-Ion Batteries from Crystal Structure Changes of Electrode Materials." *International Journal of Energy Research* 45(5):7732–40. doi: 10.1002/er.6355.
- Rights, Jason D., and Sonya K. Sterba. 2019. "Quantifying Explained Variance in Multilevel Models: An Integrative Framework for Defining R-Squared Measures." *Psychological Methods* 24(3):309–38. doi: 10.1037/met0000184.
- Rights, Jason D., and Sonya K. Sterba. 2020. "New Recommendations on the Use of R-Squared Differences in Multilevel Model Comparisons." *Multivariate Behavioral Research* 55(4):568–99. doi: 10.1080/00273171.2019.1660605.
- Schwaighofer, Anton, Timon Schroeter, Sebastian Mika, and Gilles Blanchard. 2009. "How Wrong Can We Get? A Review of Machine Learning Approaches and Error Bars." *Combinatorial Chemistry & High Throughput Screening* 12(5):453–68. doi: 10.2174/138620709788489064.
- Scrosati, Bruno. 2005. "Power Sources for Portable Electronics and Hybrid Cars: Lithium Batteries and Fuel Cells." *Chemical Record* 5(5):286–97. doi: 10.1002/tcr.20054.
- Segal, Mark R. 2004. "Machine Learning Benchmarks and Random Forest Regression. *Center for Bioinformatics and Molecular Biostatistics, UC San Francisco, USA.*" *Biostatistics* 1–14.
- Shaheen, Abdullah M., Mohamed A. Hamida, Ragab A. El-Sehiemy, and Ehab E. Elattar. 2021. "Optimal Parameter Identification of Linear and Non-Linear Models for Li-Ion Battery Cells." *Energy Reports* 7:7170–85. doi: 10.1016/j.egy.2021.10.086.
- Takeno, Kazuhiko, Masahiro Ichimura, Kazuo Takano, and Junichi Yamaki. 2005. "Influence of Cycle Capacity Deterioration and Storage Capacity Deterioration on Li-Ion Batteries Used in Mobile Phones." *Journal of Power Sources* 142(1–2):298–305. doi: 10.1016/j.jpowsour.2004.10.007.
- Willmott, Cort J., and Kenji Matsuura. 2005. "Advantages of the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) over the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) in Assessing Average Model Performance." *Climate Research* 30(1):79–82. doi: 10.3354/cr030079.
- Yang, Yixin. 2021. "A Machine-Learning Prediction Method of Lithium-Ion Battery Life Based on Charge Process for Different Applications." *Applied Energy* 292(October 2020):116897. doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116897.
- You, Heze, Xueyuan Wang, Jiangong Zhu, Bo Jiang, Guangshuai Han, Xuezhe Wei, and Haifeng Dai. 2024. "Investigation of Lithium-Ion Battery Nonlinear Degradation by Experiments and Model-Based Simulation." *Energy Storage Materials* 65(June 2023):103083. doi: 10.1016/j.ensm.2023.103083.
- Zhang, Duo, Antonio Bertei, Farid Tariq, Nigel Brandon, and Qiong Cai. 2019. "Progress in 3D Electrode Microstructure Modelling for Fuel Cells and Batteries: Transport and Electrochemical Performance." *Progress in Energy* 1(1). doi: 10.1088/2516-1083/ab38c7.
- Zhang, Fan, and Lauren J. O'Donnell. 2019. *Support Vector Regression*. Elsevier Inc.
- Zhang, Meng, Guoqing Kang, Lifeng Wu, and Yong Guan. 2022. "A Method for Capacity Prediction of Lithium-Ion Batteries under Small Sample Conditions." *Energy* 238:122094. doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2021.122094.
- Zhang, Yu, Wenjing Xu, Guangjie Liu, Zhiyong Zhang, Jinlong Zhu, and Meng Li. 2021. "Bandgap Prediction of Two-Dimensional Materials Using Machine Learning." *PLoS ONE* 16(8 August):1–12. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0255637.
- Zhang, Zhongheng. 2016. "Introduction to Machine Learning: K-Nearest Neighbors." *Annals of Translational Medicine* 4(11):1–7. doi: 10.21037/atm.2016.03.37.
- Zhao, Jingyuan, Heping Ling, Jin Liu, Junbin Wang, Andrew F. Burke, and Yubo Lian. 2023. "Machine Learning for Predicting Battery Capacity for Electric Vehicles." *eTransportation* 15(August 2022):100214. doi: 10.1016/j.etrans.2022.100214.